

COMMUNICATING ON THE INTERNET - SOCIAL NETWORKS. VERBAL AND NONVERBAL COMMUNICATION

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Annotation: This article discusses the types of communication on social networks: verbal and nonverbal communication. The types of communication and their differences are shown. Information is provided about nonverbal communication methods - emoticons, interfaces, etc.

Keywords: internet, internet network, social network, sociolinguistics, emoticons, verbal and nonverbal media, communication, communication methods, Telegram, Facebook, Instagram, chat, abbreviations, social network text.

Today, we would not be mistaken if we say that the Internet has penetrated every corner of the world. Without the Internet, our daily tasks are becoming more difficult to perform, and our labor productivity is clearly decreasing without it. The Internet has brought great changes to our lives: it has saved time, increased our ability to find information, saved us money, etc.

We can easily and quickly find any information via the Internet, analyze it, and if necessary, easily share this information with others. We can stay informed about news from anywhere in the world, and we can easily spread news from our country and our work to the whole world.

The most important benefit of the Internet is that it quickly informs people about world news.

In our country, great attention is being paid to the development of the Internet today. Telecommunications companies are carrying out many practical works to increase the speed and quality of the Internet. Through these works, not only the Internet industry is developing in our country, but also an Internet culture is being formed.

Initially, people communicated face to face, but later, after the advent of writing, they switched to communicating through letters. These two types of communication have long served as the main communication processes between people. Since the late 19th and early 20th centuries, another form of communication has appeared - Internet communication, and it is no exaggeration to say that it has become the most important form of communication today.

When communicating via the Internet, we can easily exchange ideas with our distant relatives, friends, and acquaintances. When communicating via the Internet, we overcome the boundaries of time and space.

Internet communication is when we communicate with our acquaintances at any time, regardless of where we live.

“Online communication seems to be beneficial for health, especially if it is carried out in a way that does not harm offline communication and is carried out in a way that is harmonious with it. Spending your life online, without communicating with the outside world,

may, on the contrary, lead to a reduction in life expectancy,” says William Hobbs of the University of California, San Diego.

Communication on the Internet - in the process of communication, we use verbal and nonverbal means of communication. Accordingly, we can divide the means of communication we use on the Internet into two types:

1. Verbal means of communication.
2. Nonverbal means of communication.

S. M. Erwin-Tripp considers the verbal behavior of partners (participants in the communication process) as the main subject of sociolinguistics: “Sociolinguistics deals with the verbal behavior of participants in the communication process according to the situation, topic, interaction functions, forms and assessments. The center of this definition is verbal behavior (speech and its alternatives). In this case, in order to fully describe the system, it is necessary to include gestures and images, which are considered functional alternatives (alternatives) of linguistic signs. However, verbal behavior manifests itself everywhere as a complete system of a higher level. Accordingly, it can be called a convenient starting point.”

Concurring with the above opinion, we should not forget that in the process of communication-correspondence on the Internet, we also use nonverbal means. Because through nonverbal means we can freely reveal our inner feelings. For example, instead of telling someone we love them verbally or in writing, sending them a ♥ (heart) will clearly express our inner feelings, and in addition, communicating through nonverbal means increases our self-confidence.

In the process of communication, the communication situation, that is, the communicative situation, is constantly changing. That is, people who were our teachers in one place may become our friends in the next, or our leaders may become our parents or siblings in the next situation. Depending on this situation, the means of communication in our communication also change. Our speech also changes from formal to casual. This is called a social role or social status in sociolinguistics. The social role changes as a result of the influence of the communicative situation.

Communicative situation is a situation of speech communication between two or more people. The communicative situation has a certain structure. It consists of the following components:

- 1) speaker (addressee);
- 2) listener (addressee);
- 3) the relationship between the speaker and the listener;
- 4) the emotionality of the communication (formal-neutral-friendly);
- 5) the goal;
- 6) means of communication (language or its branches - dialect, style, as well as paralinguistic means - gestures);
- 7) method of communication (oral-written, contact-distant);
- 8) place of communication. These components are variable. As they change, the communicative situation also changes.

Through these components, the process of communication between the addressee and the addressee becomes clearer, and the means of communication also change.

In the process of face-to-face communication and text messages, verbal and nonverbal means play a key role in revealing our emotions and inner experiences. Scientific research on

nonverbal communication and behavior began in 1872 with the publication of Charles Darwin's work "The Expression of the Emotions in Man and Animals". Since then, much research has been conducted on the types, effects, and expression of nonverbal communication and behavior.

We can divide nonverbal means into the following groups:

1. Facial expressions.
2. Gestures.
3. Voice communication.
4. Body language and posture.
5. Proxemics.
6. Eye contact.
7. Haptics - touch.
8. Appearance.
9. Artifacts.

As a result of the influence of nonverbal means, our communication is easy. We can easily show our thoughts about our interlocutor: our hatred, our love. However, these nonverbal means are characterized by the fact that they are mainly used when we meet face to face or during live (online) communication via the Internet, because we cannot perceive things like eye contact or touch through text communication, we see them only when we are standing next to each other or when our eyes meet.

In the process of text communication through social networks, we use other types of nonverbal means. These include emoticons, punctuation marks and mathematical symbols.

In modern telecommunications, which require high speed and brevity, informal communication is difficult to do without emoticons, because they contain whole concepts that require several lines for verbal expression. In addition, the addressee gives emoticons the intonation color corresponding to the statement and tries to avoid misunderstandings.

Communication through emoticons in social networks (this term was introduced in 1954 by the sociologist of the Manchester School J. Barnes) - Facebook, Telegram, Instagram - also shows the reader the influence of the sender of the message, allows him to clearly express his opinion.

A social network is an online platform that people use to communicate and create social relationships with other people with similar interests.

R. Solomonov and A. Rapoport expressed their ideas about the virtual form of communication in the middle of the last century. Hungarian experts P. Erdos and A. Renis shared their vision of the formation of social networks. Scientists associate the rapid development of communication between people on the Internet with the rapid activity of social networks.

On September 19, 1982, Scott Fahlman, a professor at Carnegie Mellon University in America, first proposed using a colon, a dash, and a parenthesis to display a smile in text on a computer. This symbol was called a "smiley" and has become an integral part of communication on the Internet for thirty years.

Emoticons facilitate communication, and can be divided into several types depending on the method of depiction:

1. Emoticons represented by symbols - :);
2. Emoticons represented by emoticons - 😊;

3. Animated emoticons - 🐱

Emoticons, which are depicted using symbols, help us express our thoughts in the process of communication mainly through letters and punctuation marks, numbers, making it easier to express qualities such as joy, sadness, love, happiness, hatred, pain, lamentation, indecision:

- Joy: :-) :-))) -D: -d XD
- Surprise: :-O: - 8-O or = -O
- Suffering: : '- (: -t: -e: C: - (
- Anger: > :-(: -(: -(: -E: F
- Hate: :-! :-\ ; (:-&
- Angry: :-{{
- Surprised: :-@!
- Drinker without waking up: <:-l>
- Fool: O :-)
- Naughty: ?:-):-)
- Philosopher: :->+
- Boxer: (:)-)
- Soldier: d. «v
- Cowboy: 8:-)
- Witch: <:->
- Astronaut: E- :-)
- Priest: C = :-)

Through the symbols depicted with emoticons, the author in the texts not only clearly expresses the thoughts he wants to express, but also tries to influence the inner feelings of the listener-reader. For example, if we express an idea without using emoticons in the process of communication, the listener may not understand our thoughts clearly, but if we use emoticons, the listener will understand us clearly and quickly. 😡 - anger, if we express this feeling in the text through words, the listener-reader may not understand, but by sending the above emoticon, he will easily know that we are angry with him.

In addition, another way to express our thoughts is to use animated tools - pictures. Through this, we can also convey our thoughts without difficulty in the process of communication. Through animated tools - pictures, we can express a certain action, a certain means.

If we want to express our happiness to someone by saying that we are happy, it takes a lot of space and time to express this feeling through words, but if we express this feeling through an animated tool - a picture, the other party will clearly understand our speech and thoughts.

In addition, there is another type of non-verbal communication on the Internet, which is a certain abbreviations used to adapt words to ourselves. An attempt has been made to create a special language for Internet communication. It is distinguished by its tendency to shorten, like many other jargons. Such abbreviations are called acronyms.

Acronyms (from the Greek akros – “above”, onima – “name”) are abbreviations formed from the word parts of the original phrase (the initial letters of the words are more often used), pronounced as one word and represented by letters, like other types of abbreviations known to the world in science:

IMHO (In My Humble Opinion) - “In My Humble Opinion” - This expression is often used as a result of your statement, indicating that each person has a personal opinion.

ROFL (Rolling On Floor Laughing) - “Rolling on the floor laughing” - Reaction to a joke or funny situation.

BB (Bye Bye) - “Happily! Bye” - Short form of farewell.

LOL (Laugh Out Loud) - “Laugh Out Loud” .

As can be seen from the above, in the process of communicating on the Internet, we use both verbal and nonverbal means, but we should not forget that the most important of these means of communication in expressing our inner feelings to our interlocutor is the nonverbal means of communication. Because we mainly use text messages on the social network-the Internet, therefore, in text messages, we mainly use emoticons, various abbreviations, animation tools, a system of letters and symbols. This ensures that our speech and communication process are effective, and that we can more easily convey our thoughts to the listener.

In expressing emotional feelings in Internet texts, on the one hand, we use emoticons and animation tools, and on the other hand, we also use various dialects, languages, facial expressions, eye gaze, hand gestures, etc. The reason for this is that Internet communication consists of online conversations and correspondence.

Internet chat always limits people's thinking ability, leads to a decrease in vocabulary. The level of spelling and punctuation literacy also decreases. The main reason for this is the widespread use of abbreviations in communication processes on Internet networks, the use of various "smileys", symbols that are a mixture of letters and numbers without fully expressing speech. It is an indisputable fact that in the future, young people who are neglected in such conditions will not be able to find their place in real life. Because the most necessary aspect for life in young people is flexibility and sociability, which are extremely low.

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